

CASE REPORT

Diastema closure and restoration of congenitally missing maxillary right central incisor through crown installation: A case report

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ABSTRACT

Modifying the shape, size, and color of the tooth or covering a dental implant to give the appearance of a prosthetic tooth may be done through a dental to enhance the appearance of the patient's smile. This case report aimed to present the rehabilitation of appearance using Ceramage crown. The patient presented to the clinic complaining of insecurities when smiling due to diastema between the maxillary centrals, disproportionate size of maxillary front teeth, and discoloration. An oral examination and smile design were done first to investigate the patient's complaints. Crown preparation and gingivectomy were done to level the cervical margin, followed by interim crown placement. Installation of the permanent crown using Ceramage through light-cure cement to achieve aesthetic and functional expectations of the patient was also performed. The use of a Ceramage crown creates outstanding translucency by imitating the aesthetic and light-diffusing qualities of dentine and enamel compared to traditional zirconia crowns that have an opaque appearance, which makes it look unnatural is one possible drawback.

Keywords central incisor, ceramage, dental crown, diastema, maxillary incisor

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1 | Introduction

Congenitally missing teeth, also known as hypodontia, is the most prevalent dental anomaly affecting 1.9% to 9.6% of the population which could

adversely impact both aesthetics and functionality. The teeth most likely to be missing are third molars, second lower premolars, maxillary lateral incisors, upper second premolars, and, in rare cases, maxillary central incisors.¹ Removable dental prostheses, traditional fixed dental prostheses (FDPs), resin-bonded FDPs,

or single-implant supported prostheses can all be used if there is sufficient space.² However, orthodontic treatment is used to free space and stabilize the tissues if the space is insufficient. Dental education has started to incorporate digital technologies in several preclinical training, including tooth preparation, in the recent decade, as a result of advancements in digital dental technology and to improve the traditional approaches to evaluation.³

The case presented with a complaint of an apparent diastema on the maxillary anterior due to a congenitally missing maxillary right central incisor. Tooth #12 is moved mesially in the space intended for tooth #11. Furthermore, the maxillary lateral incisor is indicated for gingivectomy in preparation for crown insertion. In the consideration to the hefty gap between tooth #12 and #21, a Ceramage crown installation subsequent gingivectomy was the treatment of choice.

This case report aimed to show how a Ceramage crown was used to correct a congenitally missing right central incisor with anterior spacing.

Ceramage predominates other composite materials on the market in regards to versatility, strength, and aesthetics that are fundamental materials for meeting expectations of

continually changing in the world of dentistry.

2 | Case presentation section

Figure 1. Congenitally missing right central incisor with anterior spacing (Pre-treatment intraoral photograph)

2.1 Chief Complaint

A 32-year-old male came to a dental clinic complaining “Doc, bati jud kaayo lantawon ang atubangan sakong ngipon kay haskang dako og gap, unya naa pa jud discoloration sa isa ka ngipon” (My front teeth are really ugly to look at because of the wide gap of these two adjacent teeth with an obvious discoloration of the other tooth). Patient wished to fix the wide diastema and enhance the discoloration of his teeth to make it aesthetically-pleasing. Pre-treatment intraoral photograph is shown in Figure 1.

2.2 Medical and Dental History

A healthy 32-year-old male patient had no significant illness found in his

Figure 2. (A) Crown preparation on maxillary left central incisor, maxillary right lateral incisor, and maxillary right canine. (B) Gingivectomy on maxillary right lateral incisor. (C) Ceramage crown installation (Post-treatment intraoral photograph)

medical history. Patient had no habits that impaired the oral cavity. Patient brushes his teeth at least twice a day and uses toothpicks for oral hygiene. Initial observation on his oral hygiene is fair. However, clinical and radiographic examinations revealed a congenitally missing maxillary right central incisor; a deep carious lesion of non-vital tooth #25 and non-vital tooth #35; extracted tooth #36; and unmentioned teeth are all present and vital.

2.3 Diagnosis and Etiology

A congenitally missing maxillary right central incisor was discovered during a clinical examination, resulting in a maxillary diastema of approximately

3.5 mm was found. The disproportionate size and color of maxillary front teeth was also observed.

2.4 Prognosis

A ceramage crown incorporated with gingivectomy of the maxillary right lateral incisor was used in preparation for crown insertion. The first visit included consultation and smile design. The gingivectomy and crown tooth preparation took place during the second visit of the patient and as well as taking the impression. On the third visit of the patient, the gingiva was already healing steadily which opted for temporarization of crown. Fitting of the crown installation was during the fourth visit. The chosen material is

aesthetically pleasing and functional. The gingiva was already healed during the final crown installation and thus, it enhanced the patient's smile and boosts the overall confidence.

2.5 Treatment

The best course of action for teeth #21, 12, and 13 was the installation of a ceramage crown. Due to its benefits, which imitate the light-diffusing properties of dentine and enamel, the ceramage crown was selected as a treatment option because it offers remarkable translucency.

At the initial consultation, the patient's concerns were assessed by starting with an oral examination followed by a smile design for the patient to envision their future smile before receiving cosmetic dental care. Crown preparation and gingivectomy were completed at the second appointment to prepare for the insertion of temporary crowns on the next visit. A tooth preparation procedure was made for teeth #21, 12, and 13 (Figure 2-A). The treatment included performing a gingivectomy on tooth #12 to level the uneven cervical margin between teeth #21 and 12 (Figure 2-B). It was to ensure the teeth looked aesthetically pleasing.

After a few weeks, the soft tissues had entirely recovered, and the insertion of temporary crowns was done. For the definitive treatment phase, the congenitally missing maxillary right

central incisor with an anterior diastema was corrected through a crown installation using Ceramage (Figure 2-C). The maxillary left central incisor, maxillary right lateral incisor, and maxillary right canine have all been re-anatomized to improve their appearance, functionality, and fit. The treatment fulfilled the patient's satisfaction, while the treatment outcome improved the patient's self-esteem. The patient received postoperative instructions on managing the ceramage crown and a recall visit after six months was required. Pre-treatment and post-treatment intraoral photographs are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2-C.

3 | Discussion

Congenital absence of one or more primary or secondary teeth is referred to as hypodontia. To achieve the best possible results, a team effort between an orthodontist, prosthodontist, and surgeon is required (if implants are being placed).⁴ The simple solution in the case of a missing maxillary central incisor is to prepare the space for the crown installation of the missing central incisor. Gingivectomy of the maxillary right lateral incisor with re-anatomization in preparation to create enough room for crown insertion. In this case, a ceramage crown was chosen as the best form of treatment to help the

patient restore a masticatory system that was aesthetically pleasing, adequately functional, and pain-free. That is primarily due to the high demand these patients endure due to the clear impact that this condition has on the facial and dental esthetics, to attain maximal esthetics.

The maxillary and mandibular dentition are well-aligned and the final anterior fit was also good. However, some studies have stated that when a treatment option is executed in an attempt to close the congenitally absent lateral incisor space, inevitable alterations take place. Dental intercuspation, such as premolar or group disocclusion, might compromise the periodontal integrity, as well as proper temporomandibular joint operation.⁵ Other treatment technique options that are most frequently used to close the anterior space and restore the smile's natural appearance are indirect ceramic veneers and direct composite restoration. Studies have found that the use of indirect veneer restoration as a treatment of choice for diastema or tooth deformities in the esthetic zone gives excellent results in achieving better esthetics, function, and is more economical. Nowadays, the use of indirect veneers is now a trend as an approach in attempting to treat wide diastema closure. According to Lisa Gonçalves, with its high successful outcome rates, minimally

invasive tooth preparation, exquisite results, durable, uncomplicated procedure, less tissue trauma and cost-effective this has become the best, by far, treatment option in consideration of balancing these factors.⁶

The midline diastema must be closed without creating an open gingival embrasure in order to successfully treat this patient.⁷ Plaque buildup, phonetic problems, and cosmetic defects can all result from interdental papilla absence.⁷ Open gingival embrasure can affect a patient's smile. Therefore, preservation or reproduction of the interdental papilla in the gingival embrasure of the esthetic zone should be considered in restorative, orthodontic, and periodontal treatments.⁷

The orthodontist is crucial in assessing and establishing the necessary spacing for individuals with missing teeth. Orthodontic retreatment will involve moving the lateral incisors closer together and straightening their roots to decrease the possibility and severity of open embrasure.⁷ Open gingival embrasures are found to be highly related to divergent roots.⁸ When root angulation shifts progressively more parallel, the contact point lengthens and moves more apically toward the papilla.⁹ The canines may also be

extruded and the lateral incisors may be intruded to establish the natural gingival level.⁷ However, the orthodontic treatment is a more complex, longer, and expensive treatment compared to restorative treatments, all of which were the major concerns of this patient.⁷

According to Mehran Bahrami et al., the alternative of treatment for hypodontia patients may be dental implants.⁴

Standard-diameter implants are frequently used in implant procedures, although the lack of interdental space creates undesirable cosmetic outcomes. Small-diameter implants are now more commonly used. Mini-dental implants or small-diameter implants (SDIs) are generally thought of as having a diameter of less than 3mm. With a level of performance comparable to standard-diameter implants, SDIs are being used to address issues with bone quantity. Due to the limitations in the structure and capacity of the alveolar bone, the various SDI designs have become more commonly used in recent years. Aside from that, several restrictions including a smaller mesiodistal space, poor bone quality and quantity particularly after an orthodontic treatment, and impaired implant locations, the use of dental implants in patients with hypodontia may be difficult. It should use the appropriate radiography to reevaluate the space needed for the

implant fixture.

Therefore, in this case the re-anatomization of maxillary right lateral incisor and canine turned into a maxillary right central and lateral in order to restore the proper masticatory function of the patient in reducing the pain and discomfort, attain the aesthetic demand and improve the confidence of the patient was achieved in using ceramage crown.

Prosthodontics has changed significantly as a consequence to the patients' increasing needs for comfort, function, esthetics, and health, and it is likely that this evolution will continue.¹⁰ In a recent study about advancement in prosthodontics according to Kokila Vellingiri, Deviprasad Nooji, et al. cited two improvements in the field of ceramics. First is the monolithic zirconia that overcomes the problem of traditional zirconia because of their insufficient translucency that is why it is always accompanied by porcelain veneering to obtain a satisfactory aesthetic. The introduction of monolithic zirconia restorations without porcelain veneering is comparatively recent.¹⁰ Modifications to the microstructure and different processes approaches have improved this novel's transparency. These restorations, which were made completely by utilizing CAD/CAM in areas with little interocclusal space because of its

occlusal thickness's capacity to bear pressures of merely 0.5 mm.¹⁰ The second improvement was Polymer infiltrated ceramics. Recently, a new substance known as "polymer-infiltrated ceramic network" was introduced by fusing the qualities constructed from resin and ceramic composites.¹⁰ It contain a ceramic matrix that is 86 weight percent of the total weight and polymer matrix at 14% by weight.¹⁰ They have elastic properties in addition to long-term durability, modulus comparable to resin composites equivalent to ceramics in terms of esthetic stability. Furthermore, advancement in tooth preparation was also introduced. One of the drawbacks in manual preparation is inadequate or excessive planning and iatrogenic soft-tissue injury, which are primarily related to inadequate intraoral vision and accessibility.¹⁰ Another drawback is that the rotary devices' high-pitched noises make patients and dentists uncomfortable. In 2019, a robotic system was invented in China to address these problems in tooth preparation. In studying the 15 extracted human teeth, the findings indicated that the robotic automated tooth showed better accuracy than conventional preparation. However, a more thorough investigation into safety, it is necessary to consider efficacy and the ablation range.

4 | Conclusions

A congenitally missing central incisor with a diastema requires an interdisciplinary treatment strategy that involves prosthodontics and a laboratory technician. With the patient's participation and collaboration, treatment planning can be innovative with a detailed case history, clinical examination, and precise diagnosis. A suitable occlusion that is painless and visually appealing to the patient was achieved.

Author Contributions

B.M.: Writing - Original Draft, Conceptualization, Validation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing, I.F.A.: Writing - Original Draft, Conceptualization, Validation, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, R.D.A.: Writing - Original Draft, Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing M.J.L.: Writing - Original Draft, Conceptualization, Validation, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, P.L.L.: Writing - Original Draft, Conceptualization, Validation, Writing - Review & Editing.

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Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of Southwestern University PHINMA School of dentistry.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from the patient and the attending dentist. All methods

have been exhausted to maintain the anonymity of the patient.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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